

Development of LiDAR based scanning for optical imaging application

(Pembangunan sistem pengimbasan berasaskan LiDAR untuk aplikasi pengimejan optik)

Sivabalan Tamilarasu, Mohd Hadri Hafiz Mokhtar

^a Photonic Technology Lab, Department of Electrical, Electronic & Systems Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Malaysia

*Corresponding author: a159410@siswa.ukm.edu.my

ABSTRACT

Light detection and ranging (LiDAR) is a technology that uses light pulses and light scattering to measure distances. The data points are collected by using time-of-flight between the target object and the LiDAR module. To perform a 3D imaging process, a LiDAR must scan the target object in single and multi-plane field-of-view. However, a standard LiDAR module can only perform a single measurement of distance and signal strength. So, the standard LiDAR module requires a modification to scan both single and multi-plane of the target object. The LiDAR module was characterised by varying distance, angles, and materials. Hence, two- and three-dimensional LiDAR was designed to perform imaging operation in point cloud 3D space, and the pan-and-tilt method was used to construct the LiDAR system. Due to the limitation of accuracy, the measurement was conducted from 40cm to 140cm. Furthermore, this LiDAR can perform a simple imaging operation at various angles and distances. We also report that the standard LiDAR module is able to detect the presence of an object which is in non-line-of-sight.

Keywords: 3D imaging; Pan-and-tilt; LiDAR; Blindsight imaging;

ABSTRAK

Pengesanan cahaya dan penjulatan (LiDAR) adalah teknologi yang akan menggunakan sumber cahaya untuk menjalankan operasi pengimejan. Titik dikumpul dengan menggunakan masa penerbangan antara objek sasaran dan LiDAR. Selain itu, untuk melakukan proses pengimejan 3D, LiDAR mesti mengimbas objek sasaran dalam berbilang ketinggian. Walau bagaimanapun, terdapat had untuk modul LiDAR standard untuk mengimbas satu ukuran yang tunggal dan kekuatan isyarat. Oleh itu, modul LiDAR Standard memerlukan pengubahsuaian untuk mengimbas pada ketinggian yang sama dan juga berlainan. Oleh kerana modul LiDAR standard memberikan hanya satu pengukuran, maklumat tentang objek sasaran adalah sangat terhad. Jadi, sebelum menjalankan proses imbasan modul perlu dicirikan dengan perbezaan jarak, sudut, dan bahan. Seterusnya, LiDAR yang boleh mengimbas dua dan tiga dimensi telah direka untuk melaksanakan operasi pengimejan di ruang tiga dimensi dan kaedah (Pan-and-tilt) telah digunakan untuk membina sistem LiDAR tersebut. Oleh kerana ketepatan pengukuran adalah dari 40cm hingga 140cm, operasi pengimejan boleh dilakukan dalam julat itu. Tambahan pula, LiDAR ini boleh melakukan proses pengimejan di pelbagai sudut dan jarak. LiDAR modul standard tersebut juga dapat mengesan objek yang tersembunyi di sebelah sesuatu halangan. Kajian ini membuktikan bahawa LiDAR standard boleh digunakan untuk melaksanakan proses pengimejan 2D dan 3D menggunakan kaedah pendar-dan-condong (pan-and-tilt).

Kata Kunci: Pengimejan tiga dimensi; Pendar-dan-condong (Pan-and-tilt); LiDAR; Pengimejan objek tersembunyi

INTRODUCTION

LiDAR stands for light detection and ranging. There are various types of LiDAR module. For example, the airborne LiDAR, the system is placed in either a fixed-wing aircraft or helicopter. The infrared laser light is sent to the ground and returned to the photodetector in moving LiDAR. Other than that, the image scanning using terrestrial LiDAR occurs on the earth's surface and can either

be fixed or portable. There are a variety of applications for LiDAR. As early as 1969, the study of dual-wavelength LiDAR systems which were to be used in shallow water bathymetry began. (Wells 2005)

Development of the LiDAR usage provides a new approach of using multi-wavelength in a LiDAR. Different wavelength offers different types of information. (Teo & Wu 2017) uses Optech Titan, which emits three different

wavelengths 532nm, 1064nm, and 1550nm. (Elsherif et al. 2018) uses terrestrial LiDAR scanner (TLS) which has 1550nm and 808nm as the wavelengths.

The contributions of LiDAR in 3D imaging are found in many fields. Based on the research (Shi et al. 2016), potential application for monitoring nitrogen stress using hyperspectral LiDAR (HSL). This experiment is conducted on rice under different levels of nitrogen fertilisation. Airborne LiDAR is used to investigate the surface of the ground or land; the information collected is used to identify various surfaces. Moreover, terrestrial LiDAR is also used by archaeologists to map out the specific details of the features that occur on the earth surface and underneath. (Inomata et al. 2017) improves categorisation of vegetation through object-based image analysis (OBIA), especially using LiDAR-derived datasets, and analysed various visualisation techniques of LiDAR data. LiDAR also plays a vital role in the biomedical field. The usage of a hybrid LiDAR

with a combination of radar, cancerous tumours can be found in our body.

LiDAR is also used in blindsight imaging. (Buttafava et al. 2015) explained about non-line-sight imaging using a time-gated single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD). SPAD is a detector for detecting light reflectances, such as radio waves, microwaves, and infrared rays. It has the ability to collect low signal strength. Apart from that, this research paper (Tsai et al. 2019), is about introducing a computational pipeline that reconstructs the non-line of sight object (NLSO) shape. Although there are limitations in the experimental setup, the image of the NLSO can be reconstructed with radiometric measurements which is a better method. This journal (Chan et al. 2017) is about the non-line of sight tracking of people in a long-range. The experiment setup used single laser illumination and single-pixel single-photon detection. And it was conducted to track people at over 50m. To summarise, it is to be said that lidar also can be used for blindsight imaging.

TABLE 1. Research about applications of LiDAR

No	Reference	Main components		
		Wavelength	Types of LiDAR module	Application
1	Okhrimenko & Hopkinson 2019	532nm, 1064nm and 1550nm	Optech Titan	Land classification
2	Salem Morsy & Department (2018)	532nm, 1064nm and 1550nm	Optech Titan	Collection of information from objects of a different land.
3	Elsherif et al. 2018	1550 nm and 808nm	Terrestrial laser scanning (TLS)	The water content of plants
4	Hancock et al. 2017	1063nm and 1545 nm	The Salford Advanced Laser Canopy Analyser (SALCA)	Estimating of the moisture of leaf
5	Chen et al. 2017	556nm, 670nm, 700nm, and 780 nm.	Multi-wavelength canopy LiDAR (MWCL)	Healthy and withered leaf classification.
6	Teo & Wu 2017	532 nm, 1064 nm, and 1550 nm	Optech Titan	Land classification
7	Sun et al. 2017	556nm, 670nm, 700nm, and 780 nm	Multispectral LiDAR (MSL), hyperspectral LiDAR	Monitoring the nitrogen of rice leaves
8	Giannakaki et al. 2016	355nm and 532nm	Raman LiDAR	Characterisation of the layer of aerosol
9	Shi et al. 2015	556nm, 670nm, 700nm, and 780 nm	Multispectral LiDAR	Improve the usage of LiDAR
10	Sivabalan 2020	850nm	TF mini LiDAR	3D imaging

METHODOLOGY

This section will discuss the development of the LiDAR system and experiments conducted to achieve the objectives. Firstly, to construct the two-

and three-dimensional scanning operation using the LiDAR module. Next, to characterise the LiDAR module and servo motor and finally to perform imaging operation for a target object in point cloud 3D space.

Construction of LiDAR Module.

A TF mini LiDAR has a wavelength of 850nm (infrared light). This LiDAR can calculate the distance and signal strength by using the time of flight. The LiDAR sent a pulse from the light source to the target object, and the signal receiver detected the reflected light from the target object. The time taken for the light to return to the signal receiver will be used to find the distance.

Apart from that, two servo motors were used to construct this LiDAR system through the pan-and-tilt method. One servo motor was used to move the LiDAR vertically, and another one was used to move it horizontally. Arduino UNO was used to operate both TF mini LiDAR and servo motors. Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram to connect Arduino to TF mini LiDAR and servo motor. A logic converter was used between TF mini LiDAR and Arduino. Figure 2 shows the complete system of the LiDAR module to operate the 2D and 3D scanning processes. The system can move vertically and horizontally so that it is possible to perform 3D imaging.

FIGURE 1. (a) The schematic diagram to connect Arduino to TF mini LiDAR. (b) The schematic diagram to connect Arduino to the servo motor

FIGURE 2. The picture shows the complete system of the LiDAR module using the pan-and-tilt method.

Characterisation of LiDAR and Servo motor

Characterisation of the apparatus plays a vital role to perform the best imaging operation. Hence, the characterisation was done based on the variation of distance, angle, and materials.

Accuracy of measurement and signal strength on different surfaces

The primary purpose of this experiment is to find the minimum and maximum distance for LiDAR to do the imaging process. The first experiment is to find the accuracy of the length measured by LiDAR. Figure 3 shows the experimental setup for this experiment. The distance measured by the LiDAR is compared to the actual distance.

FIGURE 3. This figure shows the experimental setup to find the accuracy of measurement and signal strength on different surfaces.

Then, the signal strength of the LiDAR was also analysed. This experiment was repeated with different types of materials such as brass, aluminium, yellow paper, white paper, blue paper, green paper, and red paper. The distance between the LiDAR and the material was kept constant throughout this experiment. The signal strength for each material was recorded.

Speed of the servo motor

The speed of the motor was calculated so that the servo motor can be controlled. This is very important because the servo motor controls the movement of LiDAR. The formula is used to find the speed of the motor,

$$\omega = \frac{\theta}{t} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The speed is calculated by fixing the time for the motor to rotate at an argument. An argument is an input value in coding to control the speed of the motor. For every argument from 0 to 180, the angle, θ of rotation by the motor is recorded, and the speed is calculated by the formula.

Distance measurement in various angles and distance.

Figure 4 shows the setup to measure the various angle and distance for the LiDAR module. First, the constant target object, which is white paper was

placed at a fixed distance but various angles. The difference between each angle is 30° and the distance was set at 51cm for all the angles. The distance and signal strength from LiDAR to target object was recorded. The same experiment was repeated by placing the target objects at different angles and distances. The arrangement of the target object was as shown in Table 1. The objects are arranged in the range of 40cm to 140cm. The LiDAR was controlled by the servo motor to scan the target object at a specific angle. This is to find out the limitation of the LiDAR to scan in various angles and distances.

Limitation of LiDAR to scan a sharp corner.

Figure 5 shows the experimental setup to find the limitations for the LiDAR to scan a sharp corner. Two boxes with white surface were arranged in V-shaped. The LiDAR scanned from 96° to 108°. The distance measured by the LiDAR was recorded. This experiment was repeated with two types of angle variance which are 5° and 2°.

FIGURE 4. This experimental setup to find the variation of distance and angle. (a) at various angles (b) at various angles and distances

TABLE 2. This table shows the arrangement of the target object at various angles and distances.

Angle (°)	Distance (cm)
30	40
60	45
90	56
120	60
150	50

FIGURE 5. Experimental setup to find the limitation of a sharp corner.

Imaging process

The imaging process was started by doing 2D imaging with a simple shape. The shape of the target object was a semicircle, as shown in Figure 6, and the surface of the target object was a white paper. The angle of scanning set from 0° to 180°. The points recorded the distance and signal strength every 10 degrees with constant height.

On the other hand, the imaging operation is continued to blindsight imaging. This was an experiment to do blindsight imaging where the LiDAR scans the object which is next to the obstacles. Typically, the LiDAR is used to scan an object which is in line-of-sight. However, in blindsight imaging, the object is placed in non-line-of-sight. Figure 7 shows the experimental setup for this experiment. The apparatus such as LiDAR, reflector, and target object were arranged in an equivalent triangular shape. So, the distance from the LiDAR to reflector and reflector to the target object were the same length. Before proceeding to the blindsight imaging, a suitable reflector to do non-line of sight imaging was chosen by comparing two different reflectors which are brass and aluminium. Once the reflector was chosen, the blindsight imaging was carried out with two types of materials which were box and basket.

Finally, the 3D imaging process was carried out by using a yellow ball as the target object. Figure 8 shows the setup of this experiment. The LiDAR module was constructed using the pan-and-tilt method, which was used to do this operation. The distance from the ball and the LiDAR was fixed at 65cm. The distance and signal strength was recorded for a multilayer plane by tilting the LiDAR module. The point clouds transformed into a 3D image by using MATLAB software. Before that, the initial data which was in cylindrical coordinates changed to cartesian coordinates using the following formulas,

$$x = r \cos \theta \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$y = r \sin \theta \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$z = h \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

FIGURE 6. This figure shows the experimental setup to do the 2D imaging process.

FIGURE 7. This picture shows the arrangement of the apparatus in an equivalent triangle shape for blindsight imaging.

FIGURE 8. This figure shows the experimental setup to do 3D imaging operation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of LiDAR module

Figure 9 shows the results for the experiment to find the accuracy of the distance. Two types of materials were used, which were yellow paper and white paper. Figure 9 (a) shows the result for the white paper, while Figure 9 (b) shows the result for yellow paper. By referring the graph, it is obvious that the reading of the LiDAR is the same as the actual reading from 40cm to 140cm for both papers. The graph of signal strength in Figure 9 (c) also decreased as the distance increased. The significance of this experiment is to find the limitation of the distance for the LiDAR module to perform the imaging process

(c)

FIGURE 9. (a) The distance measurement using white paper. (b) The distance measurement using yellow paper. (c) The signal strength for both yellow and white paper

FIGURE 10. This graph shows the results of the variation of the materials and their signal strength.

Next, Figure 10 shows the value of signal strength for each surface. The value of the signal strength changed when a different type of material was used. The signal strength is detected based on the intensity of reflected light. Since the reflection of light differs for each material, the signal strength also changes. In short, different types of material have different signal strengths. Hence, we can differentiate the type of material by referring to the signal strength.

FIGURE 11. This graph shows the speed of the servo motor at the different arguments from 0 to 180.

Figure 11 shows the speed of the servo motor for every 10 arguments, which is the input value in coding for the servo motor. The servo will turn clockwise when the argument value is from 0 to 82 and will turn anti-clockwise as the argument changed from 98 to 180. Besides that, the servo motor can be controlled at high, medium, and low

speed by changing the value of the argument. Since the movement of the LiDAR is controlled by the servo motor it is important to know to control the LiDAR.

Apart from that, Figure 12 shows the results for object detection at various angles and distances. Figure 12 (a) shows the result when the target object was placed in different angles but at a fixed distance while Figure 12 (b) shows the result when the target object was placed in different angles and distances. The results that were obtained were the same as the actual setup of this experiment. This clearly shows that the imaging process can be done at various angles and distances

FIGURE 12. (a) Experimental setup for various angles (b) This graph shows the object placement at different angles. (c) Experimental setup for various angle and distance (d) This graph shows the object placement at different angles and distance

FIGURE 13. (a) This graph shows the shape of the object at an angle variance of 5° . (b) This graph shows the shape of the object at an angle variance of 2° .

Figure 13 shows the limitations for the LiDAR to scan a sharp corner (a) shows the result where the object scanned with angle variance of 5° and (b) shows the shape of the object where the object scanned with a variance of 2° . The sharpness of the corner can be detected as the angle of the variance reduced from 5° to 2° . From this experiment, It is clear that the limitation for the LiDAR to scan the sharp corner is with 2° of the variance of angle scanning.

Imaging

Figure 14 shows the outcome for 2D imaging. The object was scanned from 0° to 180° . The shape of the object which is semicircle can be seen clearly. The shape of the object is similar when compared with Figure 6. The distance measured was used to replot this image by using MATLAB software. From this experiment, it can be concluded that the imaging process can be carried out from 20° to 160° as shown in Figure 14.

FIGURE 14. This graph shows the 2D shape of the object which is a semicircle

FIGURE 15. Comparison between the image with and without the target object (a) Basket (b) Box

TABLE 3. This shows the signal strength with and without the object.

Angle ^o	Without object		With object	
	Distance /cm	Signal strength /ASU	Distance /cm	Signal strength /ASU
54	98	258	101	290
55	95	331	101	451
56	99	297	104	504
57	94	380	109	707
58	92	367	111	697
59	92	399	107	724
60	93	361	104	610
61	94	359	101	438

The blindsight imaging was carried out with two types of the target object, which were box and basket. Figure 15 (a) shows the results for the basket, while Figure 15 (b) shows the results for the box. The shape of the image of the basket in Figure 15 (a) changed, which can be seen clearly by comparing both the images with and without the object. Similarly, Figure 15 (b) also shows some changes in the shape when the box is detected by the LiDAR. Furthermore, the signal strength detected by the LiDAR also gave a better result by showing an increment of signal strength value when there is an object, as shown in Table 3. The signal strength changes when the LiDAR detects different types of materials. Although the LiDAR can detect the presence of the object, the shape of the object cannot be reconstructed.

FIGURE 16. This figure shows the 3D image of the ball.

Figure 16 shows the results for the 3D imaging by using a complete system where the pan-and-tilt method was used. The LiDAR scanned the multilayer of the target object and the points clouds for every height were recorded as cylindrical coordinates. Then, data were converted to cartesian coordinates to plot as a 3D image using MATLAB. The shape of the target object, which is the yellow ball can be seen clearly in the result shown in Figure 16.

CONCLUSION

The LiDAR system was composed of the TF mini

LiDAR, servo motors, and Arduino. Pan tilt method used to manoeuvre the TF mini LiDAR to a two- and three-dimensional LiDAR system. This LiDAR is designed to do the imaging operation of the target object in points cloud 3D space. The imaging process is done by characterising the LiDAR, servo motor in various angles and materials. Blindsight imaging is an extra contribution to this paper. Single-photon avalanche diode is a photodetector that can detect a small reflection of the light and is suitable to do blindsight imaging, and the image can be reconstructed. In conclusion, the objectives were achieved by reconstructing a 3D image using the TF mini LiDAR module.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author would like to thank Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia for providing facilities for this project. The author also extends appreciation to Dr. Mohd Hadri Hafiz Mokhtar, the supervisor who guided me throughout this project.

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